

Interpretive Methods of the Second Temple Period

As partial requirement for my Ph.D. in Biblical Studies I created a short paper illustrating how NT authors in their writing of Scripture used Second Temple interpretive methods. They were men of their time. Richard Longenecker, Distinguished Professor of New Testament at McMaster University captured the import of this when he said,

It is hardly surprising to find that the exegesis of the New Testament is heavily dependent on Jewish procedural precedents. Theoretically, one would expect a divine redemption that is worked out in the categories of a particular history – which is exactly what the Christian gospel claims to be – to express itself in all its various manifestations in terms of the concepts and methods of that particular people and day.”¹

I concur with his statement, and in the NT we discover the following Second Temple interpretive methods.

The Literal Method – Acts 23:1-5

Paul looked straight at the Sanhedrin and said, “My brothers, I have fulfilled my duty to God in all good conscience to this day.” At this the high priest Ananias ordered those standing near Paul to strike him on the mouth. Then Paul said to him, “God will strike you, you whitewashed wall! You sit there to judge me according to the law, yet you yourself violate the law by commanding that I be struck!” Those who were standing near Paul said, “How dare you insult God’s high priest!” Paul replied, “Brothers, I did not realize that he was the high priest; for it is written: ‘Do not speak evil about the ruler of your people.’”

The dramatic exchange in Acts 23:1-5 underscores the pervasiveness of the literal method of interpreting scripture employed by Second Temple writers and exegetes. It is not a reflective discourse on an OT passage. Rather, it shows an ingrained and reflexive approach to Scripture for these appeals to the OT were made in the heat of the moment. Being struck by an officer of

¹ Richard N. Longenecker, *Biblical Exegesis in the Apostolic Period*, Eerdmans, Grand Rapids, MI, 1999, 187.

the high priest, Paul appeals to the illegality of this action.² Wall believes him to be appealing to Leviticus 19:15, “Do not pervert justice; do not show partiality to the poor or favoritism to the great, but judge your neighbor fairly.”

When the high priest orders Paul to be slapped, Paul, like an OT prophet pronounces judgment upon the high priest who has violated an explicit command of God’s Law. For this, Paul is rebuked. He has spoken disrespectfully to the high priest. Paul apologizes because it is written, “Do not blaspheme God or curse the ruler of your people,” (Exodus 22:28).

This is as literal as one can get in interpreting Scripture. Longenecker defines the literal method as understanding Scripture “... in a straightforward fashion, resulting in the plain, simple, and natural meaning of the text being applied to the lives of the people...”³ He illustrates the extremes to which some went to interpret Scripture literally. When the Shema instructed men to speak God’s word to their family in the evening when they reclined and in the morning when they rose, the School of Shammai instructed their followers to speak God’s word to one another in the evening only as they reclined and in the morning only as they stood!⁴

The Hebrew word for the literal interpretive method is peshat (פֶּשֶׁט) which was often used for taking off clothes, stripping the slain, and stripping off skin.⁵ One can see how it came to gain the simple idea of stripping a passage to its bare-bones-meaning, i.e., interpreting it literally. There were no embellishments, no creative hermeneutical approaches, just black and white obedience or disobedience. This was, after all, the closing appeal of Moses to the nation, “This

² Robert W. Wall, *The New Interpreters Bible Commentary*, Vol X, “Acts,” Abingdon, Nashville, 1996, 310.

³ Longenecker, 15.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 15.

⁵ William L. Holladay, Editor, *A Concise Hebrew and Aramaic Lexicon of the Old Testament*, “פֶּשֶׁט,” Eerdmans, Grand Rapids, MI, 1971, 300.

day I call the heavens and the earth as witnesses against you that I have set before you life and death, blessings and curses. Now choose life, so that you and your children may live,”

Deuteronomy 30:19.

Paul believed Israel was headed for the execution of the Deuteronomic curses. One can read of his grief and sorrow over this prospect in Romans 9:3 where he wishes that he could take those curses upon himself. Now, many years after he wrote those words, he stands before the leaders of the people, the very body that condemned Jesus, and begins confidently, “My brothers, I have fulfilled my duty to God in all good conscience to this day,” (23:1). Why would this elicit a slap? Wall presents the possibility that he was slapped because the terminology might have been “...considered provocative in this Jewish setting since it is an idea not found in the OT but one known among Hellenist moral philosophers of the day.”⁶ Thus, Paul was slapped because he was speaking like a pagan. Perhaps. The leaders may have pre-judged him as heretical for his views of gentile inclusion in God’s plan.

When he is slapped for this statement, Paul replies, “God will strike you, you whitewashed wall.” I Howard Marshall believes this to be an application of Deuteronomy 28:22, 28 and possible use of the imagery of Ezekiel 13:8-15 “likening false prophets to rickety walls daubed with whitewash: they look solid, but the appearance is misleading.”⁷

Paul had just cause. The high priest, Ananias, was lampooned in later rabbinical writings in a parody of Psalm 24 for his rapacious greed. He became wealthy and powerful by taking for himself the tithes that should have gone to the common priests. When the war broke out against

⁶ Wall, 309.

⁷ G.K. Beale and D.A. Carson, *Commentary on the New Testament Use of the Old Testament*, “Acts”, I. Howard Marshall, Baker Academic, Grand Rapids, MI, 2007, 598.

Rome in AD 66, Jewish revolutionaries found him hiding in an aqueduct, dragged him out, and executed him.⁸ Indeed, he was a whitewashed wall, a phrase strikingly similar to one Jesus used about similar hypocrites.⁹

In summary, this brief exchange which may have taken less than 45 seconds was filled with literal interpretation and application of the Law of Moses. Exodus 22:28 must be obeyed, “Do not speak evil of a ruler of your people.” Yet, Leviticus 19:15 was violated by the injustice of striking Paul. The curses of the covenant in Deuteronomy 28:22, 28 where God will strike his people with a plague for disobedience is invoked, and the imagery of Ezekiel 13 is echoed in Paul’s prophetic curse upon for the injustice.

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⁸ F.F. Bruce, *The New International Commentary on the New Testament*, “The Book of Acts,” Eerdmans, Grand Rapids, MI, 1970, 449-450.

⁹ Jesus spoke of whitewashed tombs concealing dead bones in Matthew 23:27.

The Midrash Method – Romans 10:6-8

In Paul's letter to Rome, he regularly identified the speakers of the OT verses he used to substantiate his claim that Jesus was the Messiah. In 4:6 he identified David. In the numerous references in 9, he identifies God as the speaker. In 10:19 it is Moses, and in 10:20 it is Isaiah. But in Romans 10:6, Paul does something different. He personifies righteousness and makes it the spokesman, "But the *righteousness* based on faith *speaks* as follows..." Paul then introduces three phrases from Deuteronomy 30:12-14 which say nothing about faith-righteousness. Paul gives the passage a new meaning in a Midrashic interpretation.¹

But the righteousness that is by faith says: "Do not say in your heart, 'Who will ascend into heaven?'" (that is, to bring Christ down) "or 'Who will descend into the deep?'" (that is, to bring Christ up from the dead). But what does it say? "The word is near you; it is in your mouth and in your heart," that is, the message concerning faith that we proclaim:

Longenecker describes midrash this way. "Midrashic interpretation, in effect, ostensibly takes its point of departure from the biblical text ... and seeks to explicate the hidden meanings contained therein by means of agreed on hermeneutical rules in order to contemporize the revelation of God for the people of God."² This is the essence of the exegesis of Deuteronomy 30. While most people thought it spoke of Torah observance, Paul claims that it was talking about the gospel he was preaching. Hays puts it this way: "Thus Paul provocatively reads Deuteronomy 30:11-14 not as a summons to do what the plain superficial sense of the Law requires, but as a summons to discern the true content of the word ... which has always been the

¹ Hays believes this passage to be *peshet*. See *Echoes of Scripture in the Letters of Paul*, Richard B. Hays, Yale University Press, New Haven, CT, 1989, 79 and Beale and Carson in *Commentary of the New Testament in the Old Testament*, Baker Academic, Grand Rapids, MI, 658 speak of it as *Peshet*. But Longenecker identifies it as a short midrash. See *Biblical Exegesis in the Apostolic Period*, Eerdmans, Grand Rapids, MI, 1999, 106.

² Richard B. Hays, *Echoes of Scripture in the Letters of Paul*, Yale University Press, New Haven, CT 1989, 79.

word of the righteousness of faith. The word that was near to Israel in the Law is identical to the word that is now near in the Christian kerygma.³

How did the Second Temple interpreters discover hidden meanings? It was through seven methods of interpretation attributed to Hillel.⁴ Some methods are reasonable to modern ears such as *Qal Wohmer*, “what applies in a less important case will certainly apply in a more important case,” and *Gezerah shawah*, “verbal analogy from one verse to another”⁵ while others seem a stretch to the imagination. Rene Bloch points to five characteristics of Midrash; 1) Its point of departure is Scripture, 2) It is homiletical, 3) It makes a punctilious analysis of the text to illuminate obscurities, 4) The message suits contemporary needs, and 5) The interpretation discovers legal nuances (*halakhah*) or finds the true significance of events (*haggadah*).⁶

We see Midrashic methods in Paul’s exegesis of the Deuteronomy passage. Three times Paul quotes from Deuteronomy, and then says, “*That is,*”⁷ and then gives the true meaning.⁸ The first phrase is from Deuteronomy 30:12, “Do not say in your heart, ‘Who will ascend into heaven?’” Paul omits the phrase *for us* because he has taken an exhortation to the nation and individualized it.⁹ In the original context, Moses is speaking of the nearness of the Law. A man does not need to do the impossible, ascend to the heavens to find it. The Law has come near to

³ Ibid., 81.

⁴ These were expanded to 13 rules by Rabbi Ishmael ben Elisha and 32 attributed to Rabbi Eleazar.

⁵ Richard N. Longenecker, *Biblical Exegesis in the Apostolic Period*, Eerdmans, Grand Rapids, MI, 1999, 20-21.

⁶ Ibid., 23.

⁷ For example, τοῦτ’ ἔστιν Χριστὸν καταγαγεῖν, “that is, to bring Christ down.” SBL Greek New Testament (SBLGNT), www.biblegateway.com.

⁸ Longenecker, 22.

⁹ G.K. Beale and D.A. Carson, *Commentary of the New Testament in the Old Testament*, “Romans,” Mark Seifrid, Baker Academic, Grand Rapids, MI, 657.

the people of God. But Paul shows that the true meaning is Christ coming near. God’s Word came down from heaven to earth and approached mankind in the person of Jesus Christ.

In the second phrase, Paul changes “beyond the sea” in Deuteronomy 30:13 to “Who will descend into the deep,” with “the deep” referring to the netherworld. Some Rabbinical sources had traditions of Jonah descending to the depths of the ocean and bringing up the Torah.¹⁰ Just as those exegetes altered the original meaning to suit their purposes, Paul gives it his new meaning; Moses was talking about the resurrection of Christ from the grave, *bringing Christ up*.

Third, Paul quotes from Deuteronomy 30:14, “The word is near you; it is in your mouth and in your heart.” This is followed by “so that you may obey it.” Moses is speaking of obeying the laws given by God. Paul omits this phrase and gives new meaning to Moses’ words. The word that has come near is the word of faith that Paul preached. He then proceeds to specify what this word is which Hays outlines with clarity.¹¹

(Rom. 10:8a, quoting Deut. 30:14)	(Rom. 10:8b-9:)
But what does it say?	That is
<i>The word</i> is near you,	<i>The word</i> of faith which we preach. Because if you confess
In your <i>mouth</i>	With your <i>mouth</i> that Jesus is Lord, and if you believe
And in your <i>heart</i>	In your <i>heart</i> that God raised him from the dead, you will be saved.

Wright enlarges the context. In Romans, Paul was presenting his perspective that the long-awaited exile was at last coming to an end in Christ. God brought it near through the proclamation and this salvation was as near to them as their confessing lips and believing heart.¹²

In conclusion, we see Paul, the trained rabbi, using a popular exegetical method, midrash, to explicate the true interpretation of an Old Testament passage. The Deuteronomy passage was

¹⁰ Ibid., 657.

¹¹ Hays, 81.

¹² N.T. Wright, *The New Interpreters Bible Commentary*, Vol X, “Romans,” Abingdon, Nashville, 1996, 659.

clear for the times in which it was first uttered. But now, its full meaning, and its true interpretation were revealed in the saving work of Jesus Christ.

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The Peshar Method – Acts 2:14-16

If ever there was a time when a human, other than Jesus, could have uttered the pure words of heaven with no taint of human ingenuity in those words, it was the Day of Pentecost when the Spirit of God filled the 120 followers of Jesus, and Peter stood in the Temple courts and preached. Surely, here was a man utterly consumed by the Spirit of God who would speak only heavenly words unfettered by any human invention! This is what he said.

Then Peter stood up with the Eleven, raised his voice and addressed the crowd: “Fellow Jews and all of you who live in Jerusalem, let me explain this to you; listen carefully to what I say. These people are not drunk, as you suppose. It’s only nine in the morning! No, this is what was spoken by the prophet Joel:

Peter then proceeded to quote from Joel 2:28-32, Psalm 16:8-11, and Psalm 110:1 in the remainder of Acts 2. But what makes his Holy Spirit inspired message so interesting is that he begins with a telling phrase that shows that he is using the peshar method of interpretation – ἀλλὰ τοῦτο ἐστὶν τὸ εἰρημένον διὰ τοῦ προφήτου Ἰωήλ¹ – *but this is that spoken by the prophet Joel*. This is that! His Spirit-filled words used a Jewish method of interpretation!

The Aramaic פֶּשֶׁר *peshar* means “solution” or “interpretation.”² A large number of prophetic statements cited in Qumran use the phrase פֶּשֶׁרוֹ עַל *pesheru al* which can be translated “the interpretation of this is,” “this refers to,” or “this means.”³ Beale and Carson state that though this phrase is different from Peter’s phrase, “... their functions are similar: the goal is to identify some current event with something described in a prophecy.”⁴

¹ SBL Greek New Testament (SBLGNT), www.Biblegateway.com.

² Richard N. Longenecker, *Biblical Exegesis in the Apostolic Period*, Eerdmans, Grand Rapids, MI, 1999, 24.

³ *Ibid.*, 24.

⁴ G.K. Beale and D.A. Carson, *Commentary on the New Testament Use of the Old Testament*, “Acts 2:17”, I. Howard Marshall, Baker Academic, Grand Rapids, MI, 2007, 533.

One might ask, “how is this different from Midrash?” Was not Peter giving the true interpretation of Joel’s prophecy? The difference is this. The Peshier method was more than giving the meaning of Scripture. It was saying, “*that prophecy is this event, this fulfillment today among us.*” In other words, “*that is this,*” or, to use Peter’s words, “That is this spoken by Joel - τοῦτό ἐστιν τὸ εἰρημένον διὰ τοῦ προφήτου Ἰωήλ. Peshier, therefore, is not just a technique to explicate Scripture. It goes beyond Midrash which only sought to show a passage’s significance and relevance to a contemporary need or situation. Peshier was pointing to fulfillment.

The Dead Sea sectarians considered themselves the divinely elected community of the final generation of the present age, living in the days of “messianic travail” before the eschatological consummation.... [T]o them applied certain prophecies in the Old Testament that were considered to speak of their situation and circumstances.⁵

Wall shows how Luke’s Greek in Acts 2 points to fulfillment. Luke changes the μετὰ ταῦτα, *after these things*, to ἐν ταῖς ἐσχάταις ἡμέραις, *in the last days*. He says:

Especially when read within its wider NT context, the catch phrase “in the last days” ... locates the outpouring the Spirit against a new eschatological horizon. Simply put, Pentecost initiates Israel into a new epoch – “the last days” – of God’s salvation history, when things said and done by Jesus’ successors take on added urgency....⁶

Thus, Peter was claiming that the Joel prophecy was being fulfilled in the community of Jesus' followers. They were the eschatological community to whom Joel was pointing.

Darrell Bock elucidates the fulfillment aspect of the passage by pointing to three areas of fulfillment for the community of Jesus. First is the obvious fulfillment of the Joel prophecy among God’s people. The Greek for *I will pour out* in the 2:17 and 2:18 quote from Joel is the

⁵ Longenecker, 24.

⁶ Robert W. Wall, *The New Interpreters Bible Commentary*, Vol X, “Acts,” Abingdon, Nashville, 1996, 64.

same word in 2:33 for Jesus *pouring out* the Spirit. Joel’s promise is fulfilled in Jesus’ giving the Spirit.⁷

Second, the universality of the promise in Joel – sons and daughters, young men and old men, male and female servants, and an invitation to everyone to call upon the Lord – points to a similar promise, the promise of the new covenant in Jeremiah 31:34 where the prophet says, “No longer will they teach their neighbor, or say to one another, ‘Know the Lord,’ because they will all know me from the least of them to the greatest.” Bock concludes, “Peter’s contention to his Jewish audience is that the Spirit’s outpouring represents the first signs of the presence of new-covenant promise.”⁸

Third, Jesus’ resurrection and enthronement were the inaugurated fulfillment of God’s promise to David to seat a descendant upon his throne. Acts 2:30 alludes to Psalm 132:11 which is based upon the Davidic covenant promises of 2 Samuel 7. These are combined with Psalm 16:8-11 and 110:1 which Peter said were about the resurrection and enthronement of Jesus. Bock concludes, “Jesus’ resurrection-ascension to God’s right hand is put forward by Peter as a fulfillment of the Davidic covenant, just as the allusion to Joel fulfills the new covenant.”⁹

In conclusion, on the day when Peter was filled with the Holy Spirit, spoke in tongues, and proclaimed the first, Spirit-empowered proclamation of the gospel, he also used the Second Temple Jewish method of interpretation. He used the *peshar* method, the “this is that” method showing how the prophecies of old were being fulfilled in Jesus and the new community of the Spirit.

⁷ Craig A. Blasing and Darrell L. Bock, editors, *Dispensationalism, Israel and the Church*, “The Reign of the Lord Christ,” Darrell L. Bock, Zondervan, Grand Rapids, MI, 1992, 48.

⁸ *Ibid.*, 49.

⁹ *Ibid.*, 49.

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The Allegorical Method – Galatians 4:21-31

When one studies Second Temple interpretive methods, and when one hears the word “allegory,” the name Philo cannot be far from his mind and lips. Though not first,¹ Philo is the premier example of the allegorical method of interpretation. His motives were laudatory. When he read in Numbers 23:19 that God is not a man, he wanted to safeguard the transcendence of God from all anthropomorphisms and anthropopathisms. He believed he was safeguarding the dignity of the word of God by allegorizing what he thought were nonsensical parts of the creation story, reprehensible legalities, and trivia in the historical narratives. By allegorizing, he believed he was putting Judaism’s best foot forward in the world of Greek philosophy while, at the same time, making Scripture applicable to the needs of his people living in Alexandria. Yes, Philo was the premier allegorist, and the most prolific, but he was not the only one. Qumran writers and Pharisees allegorized also.

What of the New Testament? One finds allegory in its pages, yet, one must agree with Dodd’s observation that “...such examples of true allegory are far from common, and while occasional traits of allegory may be detected in passages which are not in the strict sense allegorical, the method is not characteristic of the New Testament.”² There is one passage in the New Testament that is clearly allegorical, Galatians 4:21-31.

21 Tell me, you who want to be under the law, are you not aware of what the law says? 22 For it is written that Abraham had two sons, one by the slave woman and the other by the free woman. 23 His son by the slave woman was born according to the flesh, but his son by the free woman was born as the result of a divine promise. 24 These things are being taken figuratively: The women represent two covenants. One covenant is from Mount Sinai and bears children who are to be slaves: This is Hagar. 25 Now Hagar stands for Mount Sinai in Arabia and corresponds to the present

¹ Longenecker mentions that Clement of Alexandria spoke of Aristobulus who exegeted the Torah allegorically. He also mentions *The Letter of Aristeas* as allegorical in approach. 32

² G.K. Beale, Editor, *The Right Doctrine from the Wrong Texts?*, “The Old Testament in the New,” C.H. Dodd, Baker Books, Grand Rapids, MI, 1994, 169.

city of Jerusalem, because she is in slavery with her children. 26 But the Jerusalem that is above is free, and she is our mother. 27 For it is written: “Be glad, barren woman, you who never bore a child; shout for joy and cry aloud, you who were never in labor; because more are the children of the desolate woman than of her who has a husband.” 28 Now you, brothers and sisters, like Isaac, are children of promise. 29 At that time the son born according to the flesh persecuted the son born by the power of the Spirit. It is the same now. 30 But what does Scripture say? “Get rid of the slave woman and her son, for the slave woman’s son will never share in the inheritance with the free woman’s son.” 31 Therefore, brothers and sisters, we are not children of the slave woman, but of the free woman.

Two observations initial are important to note. The first is that Paul is not saying that these events did not happen or were unimportant. Dodd says, “For Philo the Old Testament presents a picture without perspective; it is two-dimensional, on the flat. The writers of the New Testament, in comparison, show themselves aware of the historical perspective.”³ Second, Paul says in 4:24, “These things are being taken figuratively.” The Greek text reads, ἄτινά ἐστιν ἀλληγορούμενα. Allegoroumena is a passive participle and Arndt & Gingrich translate the verb, “speak allegorically.”⁴ Breaking down the word, it is a compound from *allos*, “other,” and *agoreuo*, “to speak” indicating a speaking of one thing and comparing it to another.

Some have objected and say that Paul is using typology and could not be expected to use allegory the way modern people think of it. Yet, “Allegory was a well-known method for interpreting ancient stories of gods and heroes – such as Homer’s epic tales – as containers of higher philosophical truths.”⁵ Not just from Philo, therefore, would Paul know about allegory. The ancient world was pervaded with the stories of Homer and the ideas of Stoics who used allegory to speak of the moral virtues. Yet, Paul is different from these writers in that he is not

³ Dodd, 169.

⁴ Arndt & Gingrich, *A Greek-English Lexicon of the New Testament*, “Allegoreo,” University of Chicago Press, 1963, 38.

⁵ G.K. Beale and D.A. Carson, *Commentary on the New Testament Use of the Old Testament*, “Galatians 4:24”, Moises Silva, Baker Academic, Grand Rapids, MI, 2007, 808.

moralizing. He is talking about real history, real events, and he takes those events and allegorizes them, not to teach universal moral truths, but to point to other historical events, the events he and the Galatian Christians were living.

What, then, was the allegory? First, Paul says, there were two women, Hagar and Sarah, and these historical persons represent two covenants. Hagar, the Egyptian handmaid to Sarah represents the covenant God made with Israel on Mt. Sinai. Hagar represents something else – the city of Jerusalem which, though inhabited by many thousands of Jewish people who embraced Jesus as Messiah, still largely rejected him as Messiah. Therefore, this city is in slavery. Sarah represents the new covenant, although interestingly, Paul never gets around to saying it. It is implied, however, because he says in 4:24 that the women represent two covenants. Sarah represents something else, the Jerusalem that is above, i.e., the heavenly Jerusalem, and this heavenly Jerusalem is free. We can chart the allegory this way.

Hagar	Sarah
The covenant on Mt. Sinai	The new covenant
Physical Jerusalem	Heavenly Jerusalem
Slavery under the Law	Freedom of the Spirit

Paul moves to the second allegorical set, the children. Hagar’s son, Ishmael, represents those who do not believe in Jesus and follow the Law. Sarah’s son, Isaac, represents those who do believe in Jesus and are led by the Spirit. We can chart the allegory this way.

Ishmael, son of Hagar and Abraham	Isaac, son of Sarah and Abraham
Sons of the flesh	Sons of the promise
Followers of the Law	Followers of the Spirit
Persecution of believers in Jesus	Persecuted by those not believing in Jesus

In conclusion, Paul felt the liberty to allegorize the Hagar/Sarah story to warn the Galatian believers not to listen to the agitators who were trying to get the gentile believers to put themselves under the Law. It was not the moralizing of Philo. It was Paul’s method to use historical events to illustrate what was happening in his day.

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